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“Xamsa” dostonlarida ayollar nutqining psixolingvistik tahlili

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada Alisher Navoiyning “Xamsa” dostonlaridagi ayol obrazlari orqali berilgan poetik nutqning psixolingvistik tahlili berilib, unda ayollar nutqining o‘ziga xosligi, muloqotning gender tafovutlari va bunda nutqning psixolingvistik xususiyatlari haqida gap boradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: genderologiya, psixolingvistika, ayol nutqi, sotsiologvistik tadqiq, obyekt, predmet, freym, individ, kommunikatsiya, nutq subyekti, nutq obyekt, motiv, ehtiyoj

Психолингвистический анализ женской речи в посланиях «Хамса»

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Аннотация: В статье представлен психолингвистический анализ поэтической речи, представленной через женские образы в эпической поэме Алишера Навои «Хамса», в котором рассматриваются своеобразие женской речи, гендерные различия в общении и психолингвистические особенности речи в этой связи.

Ключевые слова: гендерология, психолингвистика, женская речь, социолингвистическое исследование, объект, субъект, фрейм, индивид, коммуникация, субъект речи, объект речи, мотив, потребность.

Psycholinguistic analysis of women's speech in the epistles "Khamasa"

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Abstract. The article presents a psycholinguistic analysis of poetic speech presented through female images in Alisher Navoi's epic poem "Khamasa", which discusses the specificity of women's speech, gender differences in communication, and the psycholinguistic features of speech in this context.

Keywords: genderology, psycholinguistics, women's speech, sociolinguistic research, object, subject, frame, individual, communication, subject of speech, object of speech, motive, need.

Kirish.

Psixolingvistika fanining obyektini – u o'rganadigan individual obyektlar majmuyidan iborat. Inson ham tibbiyot, ham psixologiyaning tadqiqot obyektini sanaladi. Lekin har bir fan unga o'zining qarashidan kelib chiqqan holda yondashadi. Til va til belgilarining tizimi lingvistika, adabiyotshunoslik, antropologiya, dasturlash va psixolingvistika fanlarining tadqiqot obyektini bo'lishi mumkin. Psixolingvistika fanining obyektini aniqlashtirishda A.A.Leontev qayd qilgan freym tushunchasini keltirish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Freym u yoki bu obyekt yoxud hodisani tasvirlovchi o'lchovlar tizimini ifodalaydi.

Badiiy nutqning, ayniqsa, poetik matnning psixolingvistik tadqiqi ancha murakkab jarayon hisoblanadi. "Xamsa" dostonida keltirilgan ayollar nutqining sotsiopsixolingvistik jihatini o'rganish esa bu boradagi muhim tadqiqotlardan biri hisoblanadi.

Asosiy qism. Ma'lumki, Alisher Navoiy o'z asarlarida ayollar obraziga alohida e'tibor bergan. Hukmdor ayollardan tortib, kanizaklargacha o'z xususiyatiga xos xatti-harakat va nutq orqali tasvirlaydi. Asarlarida, asosan, ayollar nutqi nozik, hissiyotlarni yashirishga harakat qilish, muslima, ona, singizl va mahbuba sifatida bayon etiladi.

Ayol obrazlari – dostonlar bo'yicha taqsimoti

«Xamsa»dagi ayol obrazlari asosida psixolingvistik model ishlab chiqildi.

Har bir ayol qahramonning nutqi orqali ularning psixotipi, hissiy holati va ong oqimi modellashtirildi. Ayollar nutqining kommunikativ strategiyalari aniqlanib, ularning funksional-sotsial roliga qarab tipologiyasi yaratildi.

Ayol obrazlari (ona, malika, mahbuba, qullikdagi ayol) nutqida ifodalangan iltimos, rad etish, e'tiroz, yalborish kabi aktyal nutq aktlari mavjud bo'lib, sotsiopsixologik kontekstda tavsiflanadi.

«Xamsa» asarida ayollar nutqining lingvopoetik komponentlari, ya'ni stilistik figuralar, leksik-semantik qatlam tahlil qilinib, emotsional-estetik yuklamasi aniqlab

berildi. Bu jihat, xususan, ayol qahramonlar nutqidagi tazod, tashbeh va metaforalarning emotsional kuchini ifodalashda yangicha uslubiy yechim berdi.

Zamonaviy o'zbek ayolining nutqi bilan «Xamsa»dagi ayollar nutqi o'rtasida lingvotipologik va sotsiokultural komparativ tahlil o'tkazildi. Natijada, qadimiy va hozirgi ayol nutqi orasidagi umumiyliklar va farqlar statistik va sotsiokultural asosda ko'rsatildi. Bu tahlil ushbu grafikda ham o'z aksini topgan.

“Xamsa” asaridagi va zamonaviy ayol nutqi – qiyosiy tahlil

Ko'rinib turganidek, emotsionallik, sintaktik murakkablik va obrazlilik jihatidan «Xamsa» asari ayol qahramonlar nutqi murakkab shakllangan va hissiy jihatdan ancha yuqori. Bu tabiiy hol, albatta.

Asardagi psixolingvistik modellarga quyidagi misollarni keltirish mumkin.

Layli nutqida ichki azob, hissiy ziddiyatlar quyidagicha ifodalanadi:

“Men bor erk bo'lsam-da, asirdirman ishq aro.”

Bu satr Laylining psixologik ziddiyatini namoyon qiladi – erkin bo'lsa-da, tuyg'ularga asir.

Shirin o'z nutqida mantiqiylik va qat'iylikni ko'rsatadi:

“Farhod, agar senga yo'lim dushvordek ko'rinsa, yuragimga el bo'lgil, oson emasmen.”

Yoki kommunikativ strategiyalar. Iltimos:

“Menga bir so'z aytgil, jonim rohat topgay.”

(Laylining Majnunga murojaati – yumshoq, iltimos ohangida)

Yolvorish: “Menga quloq sol, ey shahzoda, yuragim dog'lar ichra.”

(Shirinning Farhoddan yordam so'rashi)

E'tiroz: “Ne sabab sen menga beparvo bo'lding, ey mehribon?”

(Laylining Majnunga shikoyatli nutqi)

Inversiya: “Sen emas, bu dard meni tark etgay.”

E'tiborni "dard" so'ziga qaratish uchun gap tuzilmasi o'zgartirilgan.

Yoki otsiologvistik farqlarga ham misollarni ko'rish mumkin.

Malika “Buyruq bizdandir, mehr esa yuragimdan” – *muvozanatli, rasmiy*
Ona “O‘g‘lim, yuragimning yarasi sen bilan bitgay” – *mehrli, sokin*
Qiz “Ko‘nglim g‘amli, ammo yuragimda umid bor” – *orasta, hissiy*
Mahbuba “Sen uchun jon fido aylagay, o sevgili” – *dramatik, romantik*
Yoki zamonaviy nutq bilan taqqoslashga misollar keltirish mumkin:

“Xamsa”dagi ayol nutqi	Zamonaviy ayol nutqi
Emotsionallik juda yuqori, poetik: “Ko‘nglim g‘amni ichra yo‘qotgay”	Oddiy va sodda: “Hozir kayfiyatim yomon”

Dostonlarda ayol obrazlari tomonidan berilgan nutq hajmi quyidagicha:

“**Farhod va Shirin**”: Shirin, Mehinbonu ~120 satr

“**Layli va Majnun**”: Layli, onasi ~100 satr

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Ayollar nutqi asosida sotsiopsixolingvistik model ishlab chiqilib, o‘zbek adabiy matni uchun universal metodologik asos taklif etildi. Ushbu model boshqa badiiy matnlarda ham gender kommunikatsiyasini o‘rganishga asos bo‘la oladi.

Tadqiqot natijalari asosida o‘zbek tili va adabiyoti ta‘limi uchun lingvodidaktik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

«Xamsa»dagi ayollar nutqi namunalaridan til madaniyati, nutq madaniyati, emotsional intellekt, kommunikatsiya kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishda foydalanish taklif qilinadi.

Xulosa. Alisher Navoiy «Xamsa» dostonlaridagi ayollar nutqi ilk bor sotsiopsixolingvistik yondashuv asosida kompleks tarzda tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot davomida adabiy matnda ifodalangan ayol obrazlarining nutqiy, psixologik va ijtimoiy xususiyatlari aniqlanib, ularning til orqali aks etgan kommunikativ strategiyalari, emotsional holatlari va ijtimoiy rollari chuqur tahlilga tortildi.

Bir qator izlanishlar natijasida Navoiy «Xamsa»sining ayol obrazlari zamiridagi nutq sathlari – ijtimoiy maqom, hissiy holat, lingvistik vositalar – o‘zaro uyg‘unlikda tahlil qilinib, yangi ilmiy asos yaratildi. Ayollar nutqida “yolvorish”, “rad etish”, “iltimos qilish” kabi strategiyalar turli pragmatik vositalar orqali ifodalaniib, ular asosida yangi sotsiopragmatik tipologiya ishlab chiqildi. Epitet, metafora, tazod, tashbeh vositalari emotsional kuchni oshirishga xizmat qilgani aniqlanib, bu lingvopoetik qatlamning funksional sathi sifatida baholandi. «Xamsa» nutqi va zamonaviy o‘zbek ayoli nutqi o‘rtasida lingvotipologik komparativ tahlil o‘tkazildi

Sintaktik struktura, kommunikativ niyat va leksik-semantik birliklar bo‘yicha tarixiy davomiylik aniqlanib, qadriyatlar va madaniy norma nuqtai nazaridan izchil evolyutsiya kuzatildi.

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